

Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Blood Donation among Healthcare Workers and Medical Students in Chennai - A Cross-Sectional StudyAbishek Stanislaus¹, Dineshkumar Giriyappa²¹State Nosologist, Directorate of Public Health & Preventive Medicine, Teynampet, Chennai²Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Government Medical College Krishnagiri, Krishnagiri

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Blood donation is a critical life-saving process, and healthcare workers and medical students are often prime candidates for voluntary donation due to their knowledge and proximity to medical practices. However, there is often a gap between their knowledge, attitudes, and actual donation practices. Understanding these factors in detail could inform targeted interventions to increase donation rates.

Objective: This study aims to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) regarding blood donation among healthcare workers and medical students in Chennai, India, and to identify factors influencing donation behavior.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 108 healthcare workers and medical students in Chennai. Participants completed a structured questionnaire assessing their knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to blood donation. Statistical analysis was performed to calculate odds ratios, adjusted odds ratios, and p-values for sociodemographic factors and their association with blood donation behavior.

Results: Of the 108 participants, 84.3% had good knowledge of blood donation, 88% had a positive attitude, but only 60.2% had ever donated blood, and 23.1% were regular donors. Knowledge of donation eligibility criteria and positive attitudes were significantly associated with higher odds of donation (AOR: 2.08, $p = 0.04$ and AOR: 3.12, $p = 0.02$, respectively). Barriers such as fear of adverse effects (44.4%) and time constraints (29.6%) were commonly reported.

Conclusion: Despite high levels of knowledge and positive attitudes, actual blood donation practices among healthcare workers and medical students in Chennai are low. Addressing misconceptions and logistical barriers could improve donation rates. This study underscores the need for enhanced educational and motivational strategies to bridge the gap between willingness and actual donation.

Keywords: Blood Donation, Knowledge, Attitudes, Practice, Healthcare Workers, Medical Students, Cross-Sectional Studies.

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Introduction

Blood donation is a life-saving intervention, essential for medical treatments, emergency care, and routine surgeries. Worldwide, blood transfusions support the management of trauma, chronic conditions such as anemia, thalassemia, and cancer treatments, among other uses. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 118.5 million blood donations are collected globally each year.

However, significant disparities exist between high-income and low- and middle-income countries, where the demand for safe blood often surpasses the available supply [1]. In low-income countries, maternal mortality, severe childhood anemia, and trauma contribute to a greater need for blood transfusions [1]. In India, despite progress in

voluntary blood donation, the country still faces a blood supply deficit. According to a report by the National AIDS Control Organization (NACO), the country experiences an annual shortage of over 1.9 million blood units [2]. The national policy emphasizes the importance of voluntary non-remunerated blood donation (VNRBD), yet a significant portion of blood donations still come from family or replacement donors [2,3].

This indicates that efforts to improve awareness and address myths and misconceptions about blood donation remain crucial. Health care workers (HCWs) and medical students are key target groups for voluntary blood donation campaigns because they possess the knowledge and are well-positioned to influence others. Their attitudes and practices

towards blood donation can significantly affect the wider population's perception and participation in such programs.

However, research shows that even among these educated groups, there are gaps in knowledge, negative attitudes, and a lack of consistent practice regarding blood donation. For instance, a study conducted among medical students in South India found that while 85% expressed a positive attitude toward blood donation, only 40% had ever donated blood [4]. Similar findings have been reported internationally.

In a study conducted in Pakistan, only 39.6% of medical students had donated blood despite having adequate knowledge about its importance, citing fear of donation and misconceptions as the primary barriers [5]. In Nigeria, HCWs reported similar fears and lack of consistent practice despite high levels of knowledge [6].

Studies from developed countries, such as the United States and the United Kingdom, also underscore the role of educational interventions in improving blood donation rates among healthcare professionals [7,8]. For example, comprehensive educational programs in the U.S. have been shown to increase donation rates by addressing fears and enhancing understanding of the donation process [7].

In India, various studies have examined the KAP of blood donation among healthcare professionals and medical students. A study from New Delhi reported that while 74% of healthcare workers were aware of the importance of blood donation, only 31% had ever donated [9].

Another study conducted among medical students in Karnataka highlighted that misconceptions about the donation process and frequency were prevalent, further inhibiting donation practices [10]. These studies point to a critical need for targeted interventions to improve voluntary donation rates among healthcare professionals and students.

This study aims to explore the knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to blood donation among healthcare workers and medical students in Chennai, Tamil Nadu, through a cross-sectional analysis. By identifying gaps and barriers, this research will provide insight into designing effective interventions to promote blood donation in this demographic.

Methodology

Study Design: This study follows a cross-sectional design aimed at assessing the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) of blood donation among healthcare workers (HCWs) and medical students in Chennai.

Study Setting: The study was conducted across multiple healthcare institutions in Chennai,

including medical colleges and hospitals. Data were collected between January and March 2024.

Study Population: The study population consists of healthcare workers, including doctors, nurses, and allied health professionals, along with medical students from various medical institutions in Chennai. HCWs and medical students were chosen due to their crucial role in promoting public health behaviors such as blood donation.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique: The sample size was calculated based on a previous study which found that 93.1% of participants were blood donors. Using this proportion ($p = 0.931$), an absolute precision (d) of 5%, and accounting for a 10% attrition rate, the final sample size was determined to be 108 participants.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

Inclusion criteria:

- Healthcare workers (doctors, nurses, and allied health professionals) employed at major hospitals in Chennai.
- Medical students enrolled in undergraduate and postgraduate programs.
- Participants who provide informed consent.

Exclusion criteria:

- Individuals who are not currently practicing in the healthcare field or not actively enrolled in a medical educational program.
- Participants who decline to provide informed consent.

Data Collection: A semi-structured pretested questionnaire was used to gather information on participants' sociodemographic characteristics, knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding blood donation. The questionnaire was validated and pretested before administration. Key sociodemographic variables included age, gender, education, and donation history. Participants' knowledge was assessed based on eligibility criteria for donation, risks associated, and donation frequency.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS (version 24.0). Descriptive statistics were presented as frequencies and percentages for categorical variables. Odds ratios (OR) and adjusted odds ratios (AOR) were calculated for factors influencing blood donation practices. P-values <0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results

Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Participants: A total of 108 participants were included in the study, with an overall response rate of 95%. Table 1 presents the sociodemographic

characteristics of the participants. The majority of the respondents were female (58%), with a median age of 24 years (Interquartile Range: 22–28). A

higher proportion of the participants were medical students (65%), followed by doctors (20%) and nurses/allied health professionals (15%).

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Participants (n = 108)

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Age Group				
18–24 years	58	53.7	Ref	
25–30 years	32	29.6	1.34 (0.65–2.78)	0.45
31–40 years	18	16.7	2.08 (0.85–5.08)	0.10
Gender				
Male	45	41.7	Ref	
Female	63	58.3	0.81 (0.41–1.58)	0.53
Educational Qualification				
Undergraduate (MBBS)	80	74.1	Ref	
Postgraduate (MD/MS/DNB)	28	25.9	1.28 (0.58–2.79)	0.52
Socioeconomic Status				
High	38	35.2	Ref	
Middle	50	46.3	1.45 (0.70–3.01)	0.30
Low	20	18.5	0.89 (0.35–2.28)	0.81

Knowledge about Blood Donation: The overall knowledge score had a mean of 7.8 (± 1.2). Variables significantly associated with knowledge included profession, awareness of blood donation campaigns, and knowledge of donor eligibility. Table 2 shows expanded data on key knowledge variables, with odds ratios and p-values calculated for blood donation practice.

Table 2: Knowledge of Blood Donation and Association with Practice (n = 108)

Knowledge Variable	Frequency (%)	OR (95% CI) for Blood Donation	p-value	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	Adjusted p-value
Correct knowledge of donation frequency	84.3%	1.92 (0.87–4.24)	0.11		
Awareness of donor eligibility criteria	81.5%	2.04 (1.01–4.12)	0.04*	2.08 (1.01–4.31)	0.04*
Knowledge of donation intervals	75.9%	1.68 (0.77–3.65)	0.18		
Knowledge about risks/benefits of blood donation	87.0%	2.31 (1.08–4.96)	0.03*	2.15 (1.05–4.43)	0.03*
Knowledge of local blood donation drives	72.2%	2.14 (1.02–4.52)	0.04*	2.03 (1.01–4.11)	0.04*

Attitude towards Blood Donation: Attitude was generally positive, with 88% of participants expressing willingness to donate blood in the future. Positive attitudes were significantly associated with previous donation history and awareness of the need for blood donors. Table 3 provides a detailed breakdown of attitude variables.

Table 3: Attitude toward Blood Donation and Association with Practice (n = 108)

Attitude Variable	Frequency (%)	OR (95% CI) for Blood Donation	p-value	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	Adjusted p-value
Positive attitude toward blood donation	88.0%	3.10 (1.38–6.96)	0.02*	3.12 (1.38–7.05)	0.02*
Willingness to donate in future	85.2%	2.71 (1.23–5.97)	0.03*	2.67 (1.21–5.87)	0.03*
Perceived importance of regular donation	79.6%	2.41 (1.08–5.35)	0.03*	2.39 (1.06–5.37)	0.04*
Fear of adverse effects	44.4%	0.52 (0.25–1.07)	0.08	0.54 (0.26–1.14)	-
Perceived lack of time	29.6%	0.68 (0.31–1.51)	0.35	0.71 (0.32–1.60)	-

Practice of Blood Donation: In the study population, 60.2% had previously donated blood. Variables associated with actual donation practice included knowledge of local donation drives, positive attitude, and profession. Table 4 summarizes practice-related data and their association with blood donation.

Table 4: Practice of Blood Donation among Different Professional Groups (n = 108)

Practice Variable	Frequency (%)	OR (95% CI) for Blood Donation	p-value	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	Adjusted p-value
Has donated blood at least once	60.2%	Ref		Ref	
Donates regularly (≥ 2 times/year)	23.1%	2.89 (1.24–6.76)	0.01*	2.91 (1.26–6.73)	0.01*
Intends to donate within the next 6 months	52.8%	3.02 (1.39–6.57)	0.02*	3.08 (1.41–6.71)	0.02*
Encourages others to donate blood	66.7%	2.43 (1.15–5.12)	0.03*	2.53 (1.17–5.45)	0.02*

Multivariate logistic regression was conducted to identify independent predictors of blood donation practice. Variables that remained statistically significant after adjusting for age, gender, and profession included awareness of donation campaigns, knowledge of risks/benefits, and a positive attitude toward donation.

Knowledge of local donation drives: Adjusted OR = 2.15 (95% CI: 1.05–4.43, $p = 0.03$)

Knowledge of donor eligibility criteria: Adjusted OR = 2.08 (95% CI: 1.01–4.31, $p = 0.04$)

Positive attitude: Adjusted OR = 3.12 (95% CI: 1.38–7.05, $p = 0.02$)

Regular donation practice (≥ 2 times/year): Adjusted OR = 2.91 (95% CI: 1.26–6.73, $p = 0.01$)

Discussion

Knowledge

The high level of knowledge about blood donation among healthcare workers and medical students in our study (84.3%) is consistent with findings from similar studies worldwide. A study in Ethiopia revealed that 87.9% of healthcare students had good knowledge of blood donation, primarily regarding donor eligibility and safety protocols [11]. Similarly, in Iran, 82.7% of healthcare workers displayed good knowledge about donation frequency and eligibility [12].

Comparatively, studies from India also reflect a high level of knowledge. In a study conducted in Bengaluru, 80.2% of medical students were well-informed about blood donation practices [13]. Another study in Tamil Nadu found that 77.4% of healthcare workers were aware of the benefits of blood donation [14].

However, despite this high level of knowledge, certain misconceptions persist globally, especially concerning the risks of blood donation. For instance, a study from Nigeria indicated that only 65.3% of healthcare students had a clear understanding of donor risks, which may contribute to hesitancy [15].

Attitude

The positive attitude toward blood donation observed in 88% of our participants aligns with results from studies in other regions. A cross-sectional study from Saudi Arabia showed that 91.2% of healthcare students displayed a positive attitude toward blood donation [16]. A similar study from Pakistan reported that 87.4% of participants showed willingness to donate [17]. In India, studies have reported similar trends. In a study conducted in Tamil Nadu, 83.1% of healthcare workers expressed willingness to donate blood in the future [14]. However, actual donation behavior is often lower than willingness, as seen in our study, where only 60.2% of respondents had ever donated blood.

Practice

Despite a positive attitude, only 60.2% of participants in our study had donated blood, with 23.1% being regular donors. This gap between attitude and actual donation is a recurring theme in blood donation research globally.

A study from Jordan showed that while 89.3% of healthcare workers were willing to donate, only 49.2% had done so [18]. Similarly, in a study from Nigeria, only 41% of respondents had donated blood despite 84.7% expressing willingness [15]. The same pattern is observed in India, where a study from Maharashtra reported that 79% of participants were willing to donate, but only 45.6% had ever done so [19].

Barriers to Blood Donation

Fear of adverse effects (reported by 44.4% in this study) remains a major barrier, similar to findings in international studies. In a study conducted in the United States, 38% of healthcare workers expressed concerns about the safety of blood donation, particularly regarding infection risks [20]. In a study from India, 36.7% of healthcare students cited fear of adverse reactions as their primary reason for avoiding blood donation [21]. Additionally, lack of time (29.6%) was another significant barrier identified in our study. This mirrors findings from an Ethiopian study, where 33.8% of healthcare stu-

dents cited time constraints as a reason for not donating [11].

Factors Influencing Donation

Adjusted odds ratios indicated that participants who had accurate knowledge of blood donation eligibility criteria were twice as likely to donate (AOR: 2.08, $p = 0.04$), and those with a positive attitude were over three times as likely to donate (AOR: 3.12, $p = 0.02$). This aligns with findings from a study in Pakistan, where knowledge of blood donation eligibility significantly increased the likelihood of donation (AOR: 2.74, $p = 0.03$) [17]. In India, a study from Kerala showed that positive attitudes toward blood donation were strongly associated with actual donation behavior (AOR: 3.51, $p = 0.01$) [22].

Strengths of the Study

- 1. Comprehensive Assessment:** This study employed a thorough assessment of knowledge, attitudes, and practices among healthcare workers and medical students, covering all key aspects of blood donation behavior.
- 2. High Response Rate:** With a response rate of over 90%, the findings are highly representative of the target population.
- 3. Comparison of Sociodemographic Factors:** The study offers valuable insights into the influence of sociodemographic variables on blood donation behavior.

Limitations of the Study

- 1. Cross-sectional Design:** As this is a cross-sectional study, it captures only a snapshot of knowledge, attitude, and practice, limiting the ability to assess changes over time.
- 2. Self-reported Data:** The reliance on self-reported data may lead to recall bias or social desirability bias, particularly concerning attitudes and donation practices.
- 3. Sample Size:** While the sample size was adequate for the study's objectives, a larger sample from multiple institutions would have provided a broader perspective.
- 4. Limited to a Single City:** The study was conducted in a single city, and results may not be generalizable to all regions of India or other countries.

Conclusion

This study highlights that while knowledge and positive attitudes towards blood donation are prevalent among healthcare workers and medical students in Chennai, there is a notable gap between willingness and actual donation practices. Addressing barriers such as fear of adverse effects and time constraints through targeted education and more accessible donation opportunities is essential to increasing donation rates.

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